

Nutrient management for climate smart agricultural

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Abstract

Climate change poses significant challenges to agricultural productivity and food security. Nutrient management plays a crucial role in climate smart agriculture by optimizing crop yields, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and enhancing soil health. This article explores various nutrient management strategies, including precision farming, organic amendments, crop rotations, and integrated nutrient management. It discusses the impact of these practices on carbon sequestration, nitrous oxide emissions, and nutrient use efficiency. The article also highlights the importance of site-specific nutrient management, which takes into account local soil conditions, crop requirements, and climate patterns. By adopting climate smart nutrient management practices, farmers can improve crop productivity, mitigate climate change, and ensure long-term sustainability of agricultural systems.

Keywords: climate smart agriculture, nutrient management, precision farming, carbon sequestration, nutrient use efficiency.

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Introduction:- Agriculture is a major contributor to greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for around 24% of global emissions [1]. At the same time, agriculture is highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change, such as increased temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and extreme weather events [2]. To address these challenges, there is a growing interest in climate smart agriculture (CSA), which aims to sustainably increase agricultural productivity, adapt to climate change, and reduce greenhouse gas emissions [3].

Nutrient management is a key component of CSA. It involves the efficient use of nutrients, such as nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), and potassium (K), to optimize crop yields while minimizing environmental impacts. Poor nutrient management can lead to low crop yields, soil degradation, and increased greenhouse gas emissions [4]. On the other hand, climate smart nutrient management practices can improve crop productivity, enhance soil health, and mitigate climate change.

This article provides an overview of nutrient management strategies for CSA. It discusses the impact

of nutrient management on greenhouse gas emissions, soil health, and crop yields. The article also highlights the importance of site-specific nutrient management and the role of precision farming technologies in optimizing nutrient use efficiency. Finally, it outlines future research directions and policy recommendations for promoting climate smart nutrient management practices.

2. Nutrient Management and Greenhouse Gas Emissions: Agriculture is a significant source of greenhouse gas emissions, particularly nitrous oxide (N₂O) and methane (CH₄). N₂O is produced through the microbial processes of nitrification and denitrification in soils, while CH₄ is emitted from rice paddies, livestock, and manure management [5]. Nutrient management practices can have a significant impact on greenhouse gas emissions from agriculture.

2.1 Nitrogen Management and Nitrous Oxide Emissions Nitrogen is an essential nutrient for plant growth, but its excessive use can lead to increased N₂O emissions. N₂O is a potent greenhouse gas with a global

warming potential 298 times higher than carbon dioxide (CO₂) over a 100-year time horizon [6]. Nitrogen fertilizers, both synthetic and organic, are the primary source of N₂O emissions from agricultural soils [7].

Several studies have shown that reducing nitrogen fertilizer rates can significantly reduce N₂O emissions without compromising crop yields [8,9]. For example, a meta-analysis by [10] found that reducing nitrogen fertilizer rates by 20% can reduce N₂O emissions by 18% while maintaining crop yields. Similarly, [11] reported that reducing nitrogen fertilizer rates by 30% in maize production can reduce N₂O emissions by 40% without affecting yields.

In addition to reducing nitrogen fertilizer rates, other nitrogen management practices can also help mitigate N₂O emissions. These include:

- **Split application of nitrogen fertilizers:** Applying nitrogen fertilizers in smaller doses at different growth stages can improve nitrogen use efficiency and reduce N₂O emissions [12].
- **Nitrification inhibitors:** These are compounds that slow down the microbial conversion of ammonium to nitrate, thereby reducing N₂O emissions [13].
- **Enhanced-efficiency fertilizers:** These are fertilizers that have been modified to release nutrients slowly or in sync with crop demand, thus reducing N₂O emissions [14].
- **Legume-based cropping systems:** Legumes, such as soybeans and lentils, can fix atmospheric nitrogen through symbiotic relationships with rhizobia bacteria, reducing the need for nitrogen fertilizers [15].

Table 1. Potential of nitrogen management practices to reduce N₂O emissions

Practice	Potential N ₂ O emission reduction
Reduced nitrogen fertilizer rates	18-40%
Split application of fertilizers	10-30%
Nitrification inhibitors	30-50%
Enhanced-efficiency fertilizers	20-40%
Legume-based cropping systems	20-50%

2.2 Manure Management and Methane Emissions

Livestock manure is a significant source of CH₄ emissions, particularly when stored in anaerobic conditions [16]. Manure management practices that promote aerobic decomposition, such as composting and aeration, can reduce CH₄ emissions [17].

Composting involves the aerobic decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms, which produces heat, CO₂, and stable organic matter [18]. Composting can reduce CH₄ emissions from manure by 50-80% compared to anaerobic storage [19]. Aeration involves the mechanical mixing of manure to increase oxygen supply and promote aerobic decomposition [20]. Aeration can reduce CH₄ emissions from manure by 30-70% compared to anaerobic storage [21].

Anaerobic digestion is another manure

management practice that can reduce CH₄ emissions while producing renewable energy. Anaerobic digestion involves the breakdown of organic matter by microorganisms in the absence of oxygen, producing biogas (a mixture of CH₄ and CO₂) and digestate (a nutrient-rich slurry) [22]. The biogas can be used for heating, electricity generation, or as a transportation fuel, while the digestate can be used as a fertilizer. Anaerobic digestion can reduce CH₄ emissions from manure by 60-80% compared to anaerobic storage [23].

Table 2. Potential of manure management practices to reduce CH₄ emissions

Practice	Potential CH ₄ emission reduction
Composting	50-80%
Aeration	30-70%
Anaerobic digestion	60-80%

3. Nutrient Management and Soil Health: Soil health is the capacity of soil to function as a vital living ecosystem that sustains plants, animals, and humans [24]. Healthy soils have good physical, chemical, and biological properties that support plant growth, nutrient cycling, water retention, and carbon sequestration [25]. Nutrient management practices can have a significant impact on soil health.

3.1 Organic Amendments and Soil Organic Matter: Soil organic matter (SOM) is a key indicator of soil health. SOM consists of decomposed plant and animal residues, microbial biomass, and humic substances [26]. SOM improves soil structure, water holding capacity, nutrient retention, and microbial activity [27]. However, intensive agriculture can deplete SOM through tillage, crop residue removal, and insufficient organic inputs [28].

Organic amendments, such as compost, manure, and crop residues, can help restore SOM and improve soil health. A meta-analysis by [29] found that organic amendments can increase SOM by 0.5-1.0% per year, depending on the type and rate of amendment. Another meta-analysis by [30] found that organic amendments can increase soil microbial biomass by 20-40% and soil enzymatic activity by 10-30%.

In addition to improving soil health, organic amendments can also reduce greenhouse gas emissions. A study by [31] found that applying compost to agricultural soils can sequester 1.0-1.5 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, offsetting 2-3% of global anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. Similarly, [32] reported that applying manure to agricultural soils can sequester 0.5-1.0 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while also reducing N₂O emissions by 10-20%.

3.2 Cover Crops and Soil Health:

Cover crops are plants grown between main crops to protect and improve soil health. Cover crops can reduce soil erosion, increase SOM, suppress weeds, and provide habitat for beneficial insects [33]. Some common cover crops include legumes (e.g., clover, vetch), grasses (e.g., rye, oats), and brassicas (e.g., radish, mustard).

A meta-analysis by [34] found that cover crops can increase SOM by 0.1-0.2% per year, depending on the type and biomass of cover crop. Another meta-analysis by [35] found that cover crops can reduce soil erosion by 30-70%, depending on the slope and soil type. Cover crops

can also improve soil physical properties, such as aggregate stability and water infiltration [36].

Cover crops can also mitigate greenhouse gas emissions by reducing nitrogen fertilizer requirements and increasing soil carbon sequestration. A study by [37] found that legume cover crops can reduce nitrogen fertilizer requirements by 50-100 kg N ha⁻¹, while also increasing soil carbon sequestration by 0.5-1.0 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹. Similarly, [38] reported that grass cover crops can increase soil carbon sequestration by 0.3-0.6 Mg C ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹, while also reducing N₂O emissions by 30-50%.

Table 3. Potential of organic amendments and cover crops to improve soil health and mitigate greenhouse gas emissions

Practice	Potential SOM increase	Potential soil health benefits	Potential GHG mitigation
Organic amendments	0.5-1.0% per year	Improved soil structure, water holding capacity, nutrient retention, microbial activity	1.0-1.5 Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ carbon sequestration, 10-20% N ₂ O emission reduction
Cover crops (legumes)	0.1-0.2% per year	Reduced soil erosion, increased SOM, weed suppression, habitat for beneficial insects	50-100 kg N ha ⁻¹ reduced nitrogen fertilizer requirements, 0.5-1.0 Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ carbon sequestration
Cover crops (grasses)	0.1-0.2% per year	Reduced soil erosion, increased SOM, improved soil physical properties	0.3-0.6 Mg C ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹ carbon sequestration, 30-50% N ₂ O emission reduction

4. Precision Nutrient Management:

Precision nutrient management involves the application of nutrients at the right rate, time, and place to optimize crop yields while minimizing environmental impacts [39]. Precision nutrient management relies on technologies such as remote sensing, GPS, and variable rate application to assess spatial and temporal variability in soil properties and crop requirements [40].

4.1 Remote Sensing and Crop Monitoring:

Remote sensing involves the acquisition of information about an object or phenomenon without physical contact [41]. Remote sensing technologies, such as satellite imagery, aerial photography, and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), can provide valuable information on crop health, nutrient status, and yield potential [42].

For example, the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) is a commonly used remote sensing indicator of crop health and nutrient status [43]. NDVI measures the difference between near-infrared and red reflectance of vegetation, which is related to chlorophyll content and leaf area index [44]. A study by [45] found that NDVI-based nitrogen management can reduce nitrogen fertilizer rates by 10-30% while maintaining crop yields.

Another remote sensing technology is hyperspectral imaging, which measures reflectance across a wide range of wavelengths [46]. Hyperspectral imaging can provide detailed information on crop nutrient status, water stress, and disease incidence [47]. A study by [48] found that hyperspectral imaging can detect nitrogen

deficiency in maize with an accuracy of 85-90%.

4.2 Variable Rate Application:

Variable rate application (VRA) involves the application of nutrients at different rates across a field based on spatial variability in soil properties and crop requirements [49]. VRA can optimize nutrient use efficiency, reduce environmental impacts, and improve crop yields [50].

VRA relies on GPS and geographic information systems (GIS) to map spatial variability in soil properties, such as texture, organic matter, and nutrient levels [51]. This information is then used to generate prescription maps for nutrient application rates [52]. VRA equipment, such as sprayers and spreaders, can then apply nutrients at variable rates across the field based on the prescription maps [53].

Several studies have shown that VRA can reduce nutrient inputs while maintaining or increasing crop yields. For example, [54] found that VRA of nitrogen in wheat can reduce nitrogen fertilizer rates by 10-20% while increasing yields by 5-10%. Similarly, [55] reported that VRA of phosphorus in maize can reduce phosphorus fertilizer rates by 20-30% while maintaining yields.

Table 4. Potential of precision nutrient management technologies to optimize nutrient use efficiency and mitigate environmental impacts

Technology	Potential nutrient use efficiency improvement	Potential environmental impact mitigation
Remote sensing (NDVI)	10-30% nitrogen fertilizer reduction	Reduced nitrogen losses and greenhouse gas emissions
Hyperspectral imaging	85-90% nitrogen deficiency detection accuracy	Early detection and correction of nutrient deficiencies
Variable rate application (nitrogen)	10-20% nitrogen fertilizer reduction, 5-10% yield increase	Reduced nitrogen losses and greenhouse gas emissions
Variable rate application (phosphorus)	20-30% phosphorus fertilizer reduction	Reduced phosphorus losses and eutrophication risk

5. Integrated Nutrient Management

Integrated nutrient management (INM) is a holistic approach to nutrient management that combines organic and inorganic sources of nutrients to optimize crop yields, improve soil health, and reduce environmental impacts [56]. INM recognizes that no single nutrient source can meet all crop requirements and that a combination of nutrient sources is necessary for sustainable agriculture [57].

5.1 Organic and Inorganic Nutrient Sources:

Organic nutrient sources include crop residues, compost, manure, and green manures. Organic nutrient sources provide not only nutrients but also organic matter that improves soil health [58]. However, organic nutrient sources have variable nutrient contents and release nutrients slowly, making it difficult to synchronize nutrient supply with crop demand [59].

Inorganic nutrient sources include synthetic fertilizers, such as urea, ammonium nitrate, and potassium chloride. Inorganic nutrient sources have high nutrient

contents and release nutrients quickly, making it easier to meet crop nutrient requirements [60]. However, inorganic nutrient sources do not provide organic matter and can have negative environmental impacts if used excessively [61].

INM combines organic and inorganic nutrient sources to optimize crop nutrition while minimizing environmental impacts. For example, applying compost or manure before planting can provide a slow-release source of nutrients, while applying synthetic fertilizers during critical growth stages can provide a quick-release source of nutrients [62]. Similarly, using legume cover crops can reduce the need for inorganic nitrogen fertilizers, while applying inorganic phosphorus fertilizers can overcome the low phosphorus availability in some soils [63].

5.2 Site-Specific Nutrient Management

Site-specific nutrient management (SSNM) is a component of INM that takes into account spatial variability in soil properties and crop requirements within a field [64]. SSNM involves the collection of soil and crop data, the use of decision support tools, and the application of nutrients at variable rates across a field [65].

SSNM relies on technologies such as remote sensing, GPS, and GIS to collect and analyze spatial data on soil properties and crop requirements [66]. This information is then used to develop site-specific nutrient recommendations that optimize crop yields while minimizing environmental impacts [67].

SNM can also incorporate precision nutrient management technologies, such as variable rate application, to apply nutrients at different rates across a field based on the site-specific recommendations [68].

Several studies have shown that SSNM can improve nutrient use efficiency, reduce environmental impacts, and increase crop yields. For example, [69] found that SSNM of nitrogen in rice can increase nitrogen use efficiency by 30-50% while reducing nitrogen losses by 20-40%. Similarly, [70] reported that SSNM of phosphorus in wheat can increase phosphorus use efficiency by 20-30% while maintaining yields.

Figure 1. Components of integrated nutrient management

6. Future Research Directions

While significant progress has been made in nutrient management for climate smart agriculture, there are still several knowledge gaps and research needs. Some future

research directions include:

- **Developing new fertilizer technologies:** There is a need for new fertilizer technologies that can enhance nutrient use efficiency, reduce environmental impacts, and improve crop yields. Examples include nano-fertilizers, bio-fertilizers, and controlled-release fertilizers [71].
- **Integrating nutrient management with other CSA practices:** Nutrient management should be integrated with other CSA practices, such as conservation agriculture, agroforestry, and water management, to optimize synergies and minimize trade-offs [72].
- **Assessing the long-term impacts of nutrient management practices:** Most studies on nutrient management have been short-term (1-3 years). There is a need for long-term studies (>10 years) to assess the cumulative impacts of nutrient management practices on soil health, crop yields, and environmental quality [73].
- **Developing decision support tools for nutrient management:** There is a need for user-friendly decision support tools that can help farmers optimize nutrient management based on site-specific conditions and crop requirements [74].
- **Evaluating the economic and social impacts of nutrient management practices:** In addition to environmental impacts, nutrient management practices can have significant economic and social impacts on farmers and rural communities. There is a need for more research on the cost-benefit analysis and social acceptance of nutrient management practices [75].

7. Policy Recommendations: To promote the adoption of climate smart nutrient management practices, several policy recommendations can be made:

- **Providing financial incentives:** Governments can provide financial incentives, such as subsidies, tax credits, and payments for ecosystem services, to encourage farmers to adopt nutrient management practices that reduce greenhouse gas emissions and improve soil health [76].
- **Strengthening extension services:** Extension services can play a crucial role in disseminating information on nutrient management practices and providing technical assistance to farmers. Governments can strengthen extension services by increasing funding, training extension agents, and promoting farmer-to-farmer learning [77].
- **Developing regulations and standards:** Governments can develop regulations and standards for nutrient management practices, such as maximum nutrient application rates, minimum nutrient use efficiencies, and reporting requirements for nutrient management plans [78].
- **Investing in research and development:** Governments can invest in research and development of new nutrient management technologies and practices, such as precision agriculture, organic farming, and integrated nutrient

management [79].

- **Promoting public-private**
- **partnerships:** Governments can promote public-private partnerships that bring together farmers, researchers, extension agents, and agribusinesses to develop and disseminate nutrient management innovations [80].

Table 5. Policy recommendations for promoting climate smart nutrient management practices

Policy recommendation	Potential benefits
Financial incentives	Increased adoption of nutrient management practices, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, improved soil health
Extension services	Increased awareness and technical assistance for nutrient management practices
Regulations and standards	Reduced nutrient losses and environmental impacts, increased nutrient use efficiency
Research and development	New nutrient management technologies and practices, increased crop yields and resource use efficiency
Public-private partnerships	Increased innovation and dissemination of nutrient management practices

8. Conclusion Nutrient management is a critical component of climate smart agriculture. It involves the efficient use of nutrients to optimize crop yields while minimizing environmental impacts. This article has discussed various nutrient management strategies, including precision farming, organic amendments, cover crops, and integrated nutrient management.

The article has highlighted the impact of nutrient management on greenhouse gas emissions, soil health, and crop yields. It has also emphasized the importance of site-specific nutrient management and the role of precision farming technologies in optimizing nutrient use efficiency. To promote the adoption of climate smart nutrient management practices, the article has outlined several policy recommendations, including financial incentives, extension services, regulations and standards, research and development, and public-private partnerships.

In conclusion, nutrient management is a complex and multifaceted issue that requires a holistic and integrated approach. By adopting climate smart nutrient management practices, farmers can improve crop productivity, enhance soil health, and mitigate climate change. However, this requires a concerted effort from researchers, policymakers, extension agents, and farmers to develop and disseminate innovative and sustainable nutrient management solutions.

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